

Advanced Simulation of New Research and Test Reactors with Whole Core Steady State and Transient Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Scalable and integrated simulation tools are increasingly central to the design, analysis, and licensing of modern research and test reactors. The transition to low-enriched uranium fuels and the demand for compact, high-performance cores have amplified the need for predictive, physics-based modeling capable of quantifying coupled neutronic, depletion, and thermal-hydraulic behavior. This work presents an integrated computational suite that unifies steady-state, transient, and uncertainty analyses within a consistent workflow. The framework links full-core Monte Carlo transport, sufficiently detailed and discretized depletion, and multi-channel thermal-hydraulic solvers – enabling whole-core evaluations of power density, fission density, coolant flow and temperature fields. Resultant whole-core evaluations of safety margins allow direct application of the suite to design optimization, as well as operational and licensing analysis without a priori assumptions. The integrated application of codes developed for research and test reactors permits maintaining physical realism and computational efficiency, while their accuracy has been established through benchmark comparisons predicting reactor response under both normal and transient conditions. By systematically reducing modeling uncertainties, while incorporating a full range of engineering uncertainties, the integrated whole-core approach broadens feasible design space, allowing optimization of performance, safety, and proliferation resistance to advance research and test reactor operational performance and flexibility.

Keywords: research and test reactors, design optimization, multi-physics simulation, steady state and transient reactor analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Research and test reactors (RTR) serve a wide variety of distinct and critical missions in modern society including testing fuels, cladding and other materials or components in advance of full-service in fission (or fusion) reactors. RTR produce radioisotopes for medicine and industry, and neutron beams for scientific imaging. Due to the wide variety of missions, core and fuel element designs, reactor analysis of these systems must support a wide range of geometries, materials, and operations. These include many high-performance operating characteristics such as frequent fuel and irradiation sample management, localized effects that can result in demanding performance environments such as fission densities of $> 6 \times 10^{21}$ fissions/cm³ and heat flux > 5 MW/m² where coolant flow velocities can approach 20 m/s. Given such challenging environments and critical missions, the design and optimization of RTR have increasingly adopted more advanced methods and tools that can manage large amounts of data to represent such a wide variety of reactors from the simpler to more complex. Additionally, the ability to perform integrated modeling throughout the operational core states for RTR, and to assure safety margins persist with the deep burnups and associated material property changes that occur, allows whole core analysis to replace a priori assumptions of limiting core states and locations. The whole-core approach can obtain significantly optimized performance, safety and proliferation resistance together in a manner that is time-efficient and effective due to available validated software codes such as described here. In addition to new RTR using low-enriched uranium (LEU), over 70 reactors have converted from using highly enriched uranium to LEU [1] with increasingly higher performance requirements. The code capabilities of an integrated suite have been developed to meet the increasingly high-performance use of LEU fuels in highly compact optimized cores. Applying whole-core modeling capabilities, analyses directly include uncertainties or readily extend to best-estimate/sensitivity treatment as described among the examples given below.

2. INTEGRATED COMPUTATIONAL SUITE APPROACH

An integrated computational approach provides a framework for the design, analysis, and optimization of research and test reactors. By coupling neutronic, depletion, isotope-production, and thermal-hydraulic analyses within a unified data management environment, this approach enables consistent treatment of physics interactions and efficient transfer of information across modeling domains. The integrated framework allows the designer to quantify performance, safety, and proliferation-resistance metrics within the same analytical basis. It supports rapid design iteration, reliable comparison of alternatives, and comprehensive safety evaluations while maintaining full traceability between input data, simulation results, and engineering decisions. A sample workflow typically utilized in the design and optimization of new build reactor projects is illustrated in Figure 1.

Within this framework, neutron transport simulations provide spatially and spectrally resolved flux distributions, power and fission densities, and reactivity parameters under a wide range of core configurations and operating conditions. These results form the basis for fuel-cycle performance, isotope generation, and power distributions for safety-margin analysis. Automated model-generation tools can parameterize geometry, material, and control configurations to support both nominal and perturbed core states, reducing manual preprocessing and ensuring modeling consistency across analyses. Coupled depletion capabilities extend the analysis to include fuel burnup, isotopic evolution, and activation of irradiation targets. The depletion solver directly interfaces with the transport model to update material compositions, calculate reaction rates, and predict fission-product buildup and decay throughout the operating cycle and can automatically track and assign depleting materials to a variety of desired discretizations. This integrated capability enables evaluation of reactor behavior through identification of limiting core states without a priori assumptions regarding reactor mission performance and reactivity control, as well as providing thermal hydraulics with the range of power distributions at burnup states across the reactor core operational envelope.

Thermal-hydraulic modeling within the framework quantifies fuel and coolant temperature distributions and evaluates safety margins against the onset of nucleate boiling, flow instability, critical heat flux, and peak fuel temperature. Steady-state and transient models are applied to represent different levels of fidelity, from plate (or pin/rod) and channel-level evaluations to whole-core analyses. Combining these capabilities allows for physics-informed reactor design and optimization through a streamlined data translation path from fuel cycle analysis and isotope production assessment to safety-margin evaluation with high accuracy. This can enhance experimental capability, proliferation resistance, and maintain overall system safety. Both plate-type and pin or rod-type fuel elements can be modeled in the computational framework, however, reactors other than light/heavy water-cooled systems, e.g., salts, can only be treated with the capabilities in neutronics and depletion that do also encompass flowing fuel.

Figure 1. Integrated computational suite workflow.

3. REACTOR CORE NEUTRONICS AND FUEL MANAGEMENT

The Advanced Dimensional Depletion for Engineering of Reactors (ADDER) software [2] was developed by Nelson et al. as an open-source software with a modularity similar to OpenMC. Using an interface to an external neutronics solver (presently MCNP), ADDER focuses on expanded capabilities and automation in reactor analysis, fuel management and depletion across the very diverse designs and operations found in RTR. ADDER is being developed to meet reactor design and analysis needs for LEU conversion and optimization of proliferation resistance of new LEU reactors through scalability to simply handle many depleting materials in a single model and increase automation of common reactor analysis tasks[3]. The code automates depletion model generation through coupling external neutronics codes with a built-in CRAM solver and provides a user-friendly interface to perform fuel management and criticality search operations. ADDER was developed from inception in a compliant implementation of NQA-1 software quality assurance standards, and like other RTR codes developed by Argonne National Laboratory (Argonne), NQA-1 continues to be applied. The motivation for software to have flexible capabilities that ADDER possesses is the need to support a wide variety of geometries that are commonly required in analysis of research and test reactors. These reactors can have complex fuel, experiment, or control material shuffling patterns that persist over several years with many customized fuel management and partial refueling intervals. The scale of fuel management analysis can require tracking of an inventory that is multiple times the core loading. ADDER is suitable for analysis of many reactors, both power and non-power reactors of various types, to facilitate key tasks that fuel loading or core design requires with the convenience of concise input and validated functionality. Previous design efforts have frequently faced software limits with the scale and automation of depletion zones/groups or fuel management even recently [4]. However, presently the capabilities of ADDER facilitate efficient automatic discretization of models into user-specific depletion zones and now include generation of both local power and fission density distributions across the whole core in order to track fuel utilization throughout the lifetime of each assembly [5][6].

One example of a high-fidelity calculation assessed the impact of the U-10Mo high-assay LEU fuel specification on MITR reactor operation and safety [7], and concluded that the expected uncertainties for most combinations of uncertainties would not impact required cycle length or required safety shutdown margin, and that fuel elements for cores should be custom-selected if a low off-normal reactivity composition occurred. Figure 2, analyzed with ~30k depletion zones, shows prototypic fuel management where elements move, flip, or rotate within the core, or move in and out storage (decay).

Figure 2. Sensitivity to LEU fuel plate and cladding composition uncertainties for (a) MITR fuel management, (b) an LEU cycle.

4. STEADY STATE AND TRANSIENT THERMAL HYDRAULICS

4.1. Steady State Analysis with Hot Channel Factors Using PLTEMP/ANL

PLTEMP/ANL [8] is a thermal-hydraulics code for analyzing nuclear research reactor cores developed at Argonne National Laboratory. It computes temperature distributions (coolant, cladding and fuel), safety margins for onset of nucleate boiling, flow instability, and critical heat flux using light or heavy water properties. The code can model an entire core with all fuel plates and coolant channels, enabling identification of hot spots and providing feedback for reactor design optimization. This capability supports refinement of parameters such as control rod programming, reflector configuration and fuel management strategies. The code handles various fuel assembly types and operates in the sub-cooled regime. It also utilizes hot channel factors to consider manufacturing tolerances or model uncertainties. Each fuel assembly consists of one or more plates or tubes separated by coolant channels. The fuel plate may have one to five layers of different materials, each with heat generation. The width of a fuel plate may be divided into multiple longitudinal stripes, each with its own axial power shape. 1-D (through plate thickness), 2-D (thickness and between stripes) or 3-D (thickness, length, and between stripes) conduction models are available. The thermal conductance from the fuel plate surface to the adjacent bulk coolant is represented by a convective heat transfer coefficient. The code user can select from among more than ten Nusselt number correlations.

The code computes the onset of flow instability ratio (OFIR) and supports multiple models for evaluating the onset of nucleate boiling ratio (ONBR) and critical heat flux ratio (CHFR). Many different correlations are implemented for predicting these margins, providing flexibility for different flow regimes and geometry types. Detailed descriptions of these models are provided in reference [8], and verification and validation (V&V) are discussed in references [9] and [10]. Figure 3 shows sample OFIR results for a hypothetical 10 MW IAEA TECDOC core [11]. The analysis was performed for the whole core using PLTEMP/ANL, including all fuel assemblies and irradiation positions. The two gray boxes with circular openings represent the in-core irradiation rigs (IRs), while the remaining rectangular boxes correspond to fuel assemblies. In this configuration, the fuel plates are oriented horizontally. Within each assembly, five vertical colored stripes represent the five fuel-meet regions. Brighter areas in the figure indicate locations with lower thermal margins (i.e., hot spots).

Figure 3. Distribution of flow instability ratio in the whole core.

4.2. Steady State Analysis with Best-Estimate-Plus-Uncertainty Using STAT7

STAT7 [12] is a steady-state, single-phase thermal-hydraulics code developed at Argonne for analyzing plate-fueled research and test reactors. It provides a statistical framework for propagating uncertainties

in key fabrication and operating parameters, such as coolant flow, channel gap thickness, and power distribution, through a Monte Carlo approach. The code is primarily applied to the safety analysis and design optimization of non-power reactors, including the LEU conversion of U.S. High-Performance Research Reactors such as MTR. STAT7 quantifies the probability of reaching thermal-hydraulic limits given input uncertainties and nominal reactor operating conditions.

Each STAT7 model represents a stripe-wise channel model, encompassing all plates and coolant channels of a single fuel element, and the next release extends coverage to the full core. Within each axial node of every stripe, the code computes coolant, cladding, and fuel temperatures, along with the local heat flux, pressure, and thermal margins. By executing many stochastic histories with varied fabrication and operational parameters, STAT7 determines the limiting reactor power at which a specified probability of onset of nucleate boiling (ONB) or onset of flow instability (OFI) occurrence is reached. The thermal-hydraulic solver is based on steady-state momentum/energy-balance equations using temperature- and pressure-dependent material properties and supports geometries with fins, end channels, and bypass flow paths. Fluid properties may be calculated from internally fitted correlations or from the IAPWS-IF97 formulation for light-water coolant. STAT7 employs built-in correlations to predict ONB and OFI. Various features of the code have been verified extensively. Further details on the code structure, statistical treatment, and verification methodology are provided in [12] and [13].

4.3. Transient Analysis Using PARET/ANL

PARET/ANL [14] is a point-kinetics and thermal-hydraulics code developed at Argonne for analyzing transient behavior of research and test reactors. It simulates the reactor's dynamic response to reactivity insertions and loss-of-flow. The code models flow and heat transfer coupled with point kinetics equations, representing the whole core with a set of parallel channels cooled by light or heavy water. Heat conduction through the fuel, cladding, and optional gap regions is treated radially, while coolant flow and energy transport are modeled axially using a transient one-dimensional formulation. Temperature-dependent thermal properties are used for both solid and coolant materials, including pressure-dependent fit functions for coolant properties, enabling accurate treatment of conduction, convection, subcooled nucleate boiling, and transition boiling. The code includes models for forced and natural convection cooling, decay heat after shutdown, control rod reactivity versus time or position, time-dependent flow boundary conditions, and trip logic for conditions including reactor period, power, and flow. The code incorporates correlations for evaluating ONB, OFI, and CHF conditions, which may be used to determine margins to safety and operational limits during postulated accidents. Feedback mechanisms include fuel Doppler, coolant temperature and density effects, and coolant displacement by cladding thermal expansion, all of which contribute to time-dependent reactivity changes. The point-kinetics equations are integrated using a modified Runge-Kutta method that provides stable solutions even for rapid transients.

Extensive V&V has been performed for PARET/ANL to confirm both its steady-state and transient capabilities. Benchmark studies of Special Power Excursion Reactor Tests (SPERT) experiments validated the code's treatment of rapid reactivity insertion events, establishing the foundation for its continued development. These benchmarks provided key comparisons of measured and predicted peak power, energy release, and cladding-surface temperature, demonstrating reliable transient modeling while yielding results generally conservative for thermal limits. An example is provided in Figure 4. Code development has continued, incorporating improved correlations, updated material properties, and extended validation datasets to support ongoing use in safety analysis of research reactors worldwide. Further details on the code structure, model assumptions, and V&V methodology are provided in References [14] and [15].

5. ROLE OF MULTI-PHYSICS SIMULATIONS IN DESIGN AND LICENSING

Multi-physics simulations form the analytical foundation linking reactor design activities to design optimization and licensing demonstration. While Section 2 described the computational workflow, this section focuses on directly supporting broader design and regulatory objectives – namely, optimization of reactor performance, operational flexibility and proliferation resistance, quantification of safety margins, and reduction of modeling uncertainty. From both an operational and licensing perspective,

Figure 4. Comparisons of PARET/ANL predictions of peak power, energy at peak power, and surface cladding temperature at peak power to the SPERT-IV D-12/25 experiment with 5000 GPM flow [15].

multi-physics tools provide performance and operational metrics, and defensible physics-based evidence that design limits are maintained under all normal and credible upset conditions. Validated codes, supported by benchmark comparisons and uncertainty quantification, enable analysts to assess the reactor’s operational envelope, such as neutron fluxes, power peaking, control-rod worth, excess reactivity, and shutdown margins from the neutronics perspective, and thermal margins from the thermal hydraulic perspective. These analyses form the quantitative foundation for establishing design limits, defining technical specifications, and verifying safety margins within a safety analysis report. By systematically reducing modeling uncertainties in reactor physics and thermal-hydraulic predictions, the models not only enhance regulatory confidence but also enable exploration of a wider design space – one in which performance, safety, and proliferation resistance can be optimized.

A critical aspect of this process lies in demonstrating that spatial and temporal discretization choices are appropriate for the intended evaluation, ensuring that results are both accurate and computationally efficient. Studies examining depletion-mesh resolution and power-distribution fidelity illustrate how numerical resolution influences predicted behavior and design margins. In depletion modeling, for example, tests comparing individual-plate, grouped-plate (three plates in each group), and least discretized (all fuel plates in an assembly grouped into one material) configurations for a representative reactor core showed that the grouped-plate approach produced isotopic evolution nearly identical to the high-fidelity individual-plate model while significantly reducing runtime (Figure 5a). Similarly, for thermal-hydraulic safety analyses, comparisons of one-dimensional and 2-D heat-transfer representations confirmed that simplified 1-D models with properly selected lateral stripe widths can conservatively bound detailed 2-D solutions. In one such study, an eight-stripe model was found to reproduce the essential features (e.g., heat flux) of the two-dimensional solution, maintaining adequate safety margins while enabling efficient whole-core evaluation (Figure 5b). Together, these results demonstrate that appropriately chosen simplifications preserve the accuracy required for safety evaluations while ensuring that model complexity remains compatible with iterative design analysis and operational assessment.

Temporal discretization exhibits similar efficiency–accuracy trade-offs: by employing higher-order integration and adaptive time stepping, one can reduce the number of burnup or transient steps while preserving fidelity in target evaluations. For depletion, the ADDER depletion solver’s predictor–corrector scheme is designed to deliver accurate nuclide inventories on coarse time grids—the predictor advances isotopics using cross sections from the previous time step, and the corrector updates flux/cross sections with the predicted composition until reaction-rates and nuclides mass-balance accuracy requirements are met—so that step sizes can be chosen based on burnup increment without biasing the calculation results (e.g., k-effective, power distribution, or decay heat).

Such demonstrations are critical not only for regulatory credibility but also for reducing modeling uncertainties and expanding the feasible envelope of design optimization and operational flexibility. When discretization fidelity and uncertainty are explicitly characterized, analysts can quantify the true physical margins rather than rely on arbitrary conservatism. This approach enables more confident trade-offs between different design criteria – such as maximizing experimental flux, minimizing special nuclear material inventories, and maintaining robust thermal-hydraulic safety margins. Ultimately, validated multi-physics simulations serve as a unifying tool that bridges physics-based understanding with engineering judgment, supporting the regulatory mission of safety assurance, informing operational strategies and experimental planning, strengthening the technical foundation for advancing high-performance, proliferation-resistant reactor concepts.

Figure 5. Discretization of (a) material/geometry for depletion and (b) geometry for thermal hydraulics for analysis of a plate-type reactor with detailed discretization throughout the whole core.

6. SUMMARY

This work presented an integrated computational suite approach for the advanced simulation of research and test reactors, enabling consistent evaluation of neutronic, depletion, and thermal-hydraulic behavior across steady-state and transient conditions. By linking detailed Monte Carlo transport, depletion, and multi-channel thermal-hydraulic models within a unified workflow, the methodology provides a physics-based foundation for design optimization, operational and performance assessment, and safety demonstration. The framework reduces data translation errors, ensures model traceability, and supports efficient iteration between core design, fuel management, and safety analysis. Applications of this approach using codes – ADDER (with MCNP), PLTEMP/ANL, STAT7, and PARET/ANL – illustrate its flexibility across the full reactor lifecycle. The combination of steady-state evaluations and transient simulations, directly accounting for uncertainties or through a best-estimate/sensitivity treatment offers comprehensive quantification of operating margins and system response. Benchmark comparisons and verification exercises confirm that the models reliably predict critical parameters such as power/fission densities, thermal margins, temperature distributions, and reactivity feedback, providing results that are both physically realistic and conservative for licensing purposes.

Beyond regulatory credibility, this integrated simulation environment has been engaged to support multiple existing and potential new research reactor operators and vendors in design space optimization. The ability to quantify uncertainties allows for balanced consideration of performance, safety, operational flexibility and proliferation resistance objectives. Such capability is central to current LEU conversion and new reactor design efforts under programs such as PRO-X, supporting data-driven decisions on geometry refinement, reflector configuration, and fuel management strategies, and operational planning across the reactor core. The continued refinement and coupling of these tools will

further enhance their predictive capability, enabling high-fidelity modeling of next-generation research and test reactors. This progression toward integrated simulations, with appropriate incorporation of multi-physics as-needed, strengthens the technical basis for design qualification, regulatory review, and operation of proliferation-resistant, high-performance reactor systems.

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